

Characterization of a Novel Variable Friction Connection for Semi-Active Cladding System

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Abstract

Cladding systems are conventionally designed to serve architectural purposes and protect occupants from the environment. Some research has been conducted in altering the cladding system in order to provide additional protection against natural and man-made hazards. The vast majority of these solutions are passive energy dissipators, applicable to the mitigation of single types of hazards. In this paper, we propose a novel semi-active variable friction device that could act as a connector linking a cladding panel to the structural system. Because of its semi-active capabilities, the device, here termed variable friction cladding connection (VFCC), could be utilized to mitigate different hazards, either considered individually or combined, also known as multi-hazards. The VFCC consists of two sets of sliding friction plates onto which a variable normal force can be applied through an actuated toggle system. A static model is derived to relate the device's Coulomb friction force to the actuator stroke. This model is integrated into a dynamic friction model to characterize the device's dynamic behavior. A prototype of the VFCC is constructed using 3D printing. The prototype is tested under harmonic excitations to identify the model parameters and characterized on a set of non-stationary excitations under different actuator stroke lengths. Results show good agreement between the model and experimental data, demonstrating that the device functions as-designed.

Keywords: Semi-active damper; Variable friction; Cladding connection; Multi-hazard mitigation; High performance control systems; 3D printing.

1. Introduction

Performance-based design (PBD) of civil structures is a design strategy that consists of sizing structural stiffness and supplemental damping in order to restrict structural motion to prescribed levels of performance. Often, PBD leads to substantial savings on materials by enabling lighter structural systems, and also provides enhanced protection against natural and man-made hazards as well as more uninterrupted serviceability [1].

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6 However, in the case where there are multiple excitations either individually considered or combined, termed
7 multi-hazards, a PBD approach becomes difficult to implement because it requires a high level of redundancy,
8 as discussed in early research on passive mitigation of multi-hazards [2, 3]. In particular, passive supplemental
9 energy dissipation systems typically have limited performance bandwidth [4, 5], and are therefore restrained
10 to achieving the prescribed performance for single types of hazards.

11 Alternatively, one can utilize semi-active, hybrid, and active structural control systems, here termed high
12 performance control systems (HPCS). HPCS have been proposed due to their potential to substantially
13 enhance structural performance in comparison with traditional passive mitigation systems, as they can
14 perform over a wide excitation bandwidth, ideal for multi-hazard mitigation. Examples of HPCS can be
15 found in Refs. [6, 7, 8, 9]. These devices include variable fluid, variable stiffness, variable orifice, and variable
16 friction mechanisms.

17 Here we propose a novel semi-active modified friction cladding connection, termed variable friction
18 cladding connection (VFCC), that leverages the motion of cladding to reduce the effects of natural and
19 made-made hazards on the structural system. Early work on structural control using cladding panels in-
20 cludes double-layer foam cladding [10], tube-core cladding [11], and sacrificial panels composed of foam-based
21 materials [12, 13, 14], all geared towards mitigation of blast loads. A considerable challenge with these pan-
22 els is their low performance versus low-frequency loads and their relatively high costs. Energy dissipation
23 through cladding connections have also been considered. Goodno *et al.* [15] studied ductile connections
24 to dissipate energy through plastic deformations and therefore reduce inter-story drift. Baird *et al.* [16]
25 explored a U-shaped flexural plates connection to passively dissipate seismic energy. Mannetes and Mermari
26 [17] reviewed utilizations of cladding panel systems as energy dissipators for seismic loads. Amadio and
27 Bedon [18] proposed a viscoelastic spider connection for mitigating blast loads.

28 All of the surveyed energy dissipation mechanisms based on cladding panels or connections are passive
29 dissipation strategies. Various HPCS based on variable friction have been explored for structural control
30 applications. Their variable control force is based on a variable normal force applied onto a sliding interface.
31 Examples of variable friction devices in literature include electromagnetic- [19], electromechanical- [20, 21],
32 hydraulic- [22, 23], piezoelectric- [24, 25, 26, 27], pneumatic- [28, 29], and magnetorheological- [30, 31, 32]
33 based technologies. **The proposed device leverages the advantages of HPCS to create a cladding connection
34 capable of mitigation performance over a wide range of frequencies, therefore making it an excellent candidate
35 for multi-hazard applications. Also, because it is designed to dissipate energy through elastic deformations,
36 the device does not need replacement after a wind or seismic event.**

37 The VFCC is designed to dissipate energy through two sets of sliding plates connecting cladding to the
38 structural frame. Friction is produced by an actuator that varies the normal force on the sliding plates via a
39 toggle system. The mechanism is designed to provide protection against blast and for daily operations when it

40 is in a passive mode. It can be actuated to provide wind and seismic resistance through strategically varying
 41 the normal force via a feedback system. This paper introduces the VFCC as an alternative to traditional
 42 cladding connections, potentially transforming traditional cladding panels into multifunction systems capable
 43 of maintaining architectural feature while providing enhanced structural resiliency. A dynamic model for
 44 the VFCC is developed and experimentally verified on a 3D printed prototype.

45 The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides the theoretical background on the variable friction
 46 connection. Section 3 presents the dynamic model of the semi-active damper. Section 4 identifies the dynamic
 47 model parameters using the response of the VFCC subjected to harmonic excitations under various levels of
 48 an applied normal force. Section 5 validates the tuned dynamic model of the prototype by subjecting the
 49 VFCC to non-stationary excitations. Section 6 concludes the paper.

50 2. Variable Friction Cladding Connection

51 A schematic of the VFCC friction mechanism is shown in Fig. 1(a). It consists of two sets of friction plates
 52 onto which a normal force is applied via toggles. The device includes blocks preventing the toggles from
 53 moving beyond a vertical alignment when pushed. An electromagnetic-based [33] or piezoelectric-based
 54 [27] actuation can be used, for example, to vary the friction force. A possible installation of the device
 55 is its embedment in a floor slab, transmitting the lateral force from the cladding system to the structural
 56 frame. A representative schematic of the installation within a floor slab is shown in Fig. 1(b). The device
 57 is engineered to include an impact rubber bumper to prevent the sliding friction plates from colliding (not
 58 shown in Fig. 1(b)). In this configuration, the VFCC provides lateral support only. The gravitational
 59 system is considered as decoupled and gravity resistance is provided by a conventional gravity connection.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the VFCC: (a) friction mechanism and (b) possible installation in a floor slab (top view).

60 The semi-active device is designed to achieve three different damping configurations:

- 61 1. Toggles fully locked, daily operations and blast loads. Both toggles are pushed vertically, leading to
 62 the device locking in a high friction mode. This is the passive mode, since no power input is required

63 to maintain the toggles in the locked position. This configuration behaves as a rigid connector for daily
64 operations and the system performs similar to any conventional cladding system with high stiffness.
65 This configuration is also used to mitigate blast loads. Assuming that the cladding itself resists the
66 blast force, the impact force will exceed the static friction resulting in slippage of the connection,
67 therefore dissipating blast energy through friction without delay.

68 2. Toggles semi-locked, extreme wind and seismic loads. The device performs as a variable friction
69 damper under a control force. This particular configuration is employed to control interstory drift to
70 limit damage to cladding (e.g. under extreme wind or seismic events).

71 3. Toggles retracted, high wind loads. The friction plates are fully disengaged, allowing the plate to slide
72 freely, and the resistance provided by the connection is minimal. This configuration is also passive (no
73 power input once the toggles are retracted), and can be used to limit acceleration transfer to floors.

74 *2.1. Friction Mechanism*

75 In what follows, the Coulomb friction force generated by the device is derived as a function of the actuator
76 stroke. In the next section, a dynamic model building on these findings will be presented to characterize the
77 device's behavior during sliding motion.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the VFCC: (a) diagram of forces and (b) dimensional configuration.

78 The force diagram of the VFCC is illustrated in Fig. 2(a). The actuator force F_a generates an axial force
79 T on the toggles, which in turn produces a normal force N on the friction plates. These forces are written

$$T = k_t \Delta l_t \quad (1)$$

$$N = k_p \Delta h_p \quad (2)$$

$$N = 2T \sin \theta \quad (3)$$

80 where k_t and k_p are the toggles and friction plates stiffnesses, respectively, θ is the angle between toggle and
 81 plate as shown in Fig. 2(b); and Δl_t and Δh_p are the geometric deformations of the toggles and friction
 82 plates, with

$$\Delta l_t = l_{t,0} - l_t \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta h_p = h_{p,0} - h_p \quad (5)$$

83 where l_t is the length of the toggles, h_p the thickness of the friction plates, and subscript 0 relates to the
 84 initial values. The distance H between the outer surfaces of both plates is given by

$$H = 2(h_p + l_t \sin \theta) \quad (6)$$

85 Since both the top and bottom friction plates are restrained (e.g., by a concrete slab), H remains constant
 86 and the deformation of the friction plates is written

$$\Delta h_p = l_t \sin \theta - l_{t,0} \sin \theta_0 \quad (7)$$

87 where θ_0 is the initial angle between the toggles and the friction plates. Substituting Eqs. (1) and (2) into
 88 Eq. (3) yields the following expression for Δh_p

$$\Delta h_p = \frac{2k_t}{k_p} (l_{t,0} - l_t) \sin \theta \quad (8)$$

89 Using Eqs. (7) and (8) gives an expression for l_t as a function of θ , where

$$l_t = l_{t,0} \left(\frac{k}{k_p} + \frac{k \sin \theta_0}{2k_t \sin \theta} \right) \quad (9)$$

with

$$k = \frac{2k_t k_p}{2k_t + k_p} \quad (10)$$

90 Similarly, an expression for h_p as a function of θ can be obtained by substituting Eq. (9) into Eq. (7):

$$h_p = h_{p,0} - \frac{k}{k_p} l_{t,0} (\sin \theta - \sin \theta_0) \quad (11)$$

91 and an expression for N as a function of θ using Eq. (11) and Eq. (2):

$$N = k l_{t,0} (\sin \theta - \sin \theta_0) \quad (12)$$

92

The geometric relationship between actuator stroke s and θ can be given using Eq. (9):

$$\begin{aligned} s &= 2(l_{t,0} \cos \theta_0 - l_t \cos \theta) \\ &= 2l_{t,0} \left[\cos \theta_0 - \frac{\sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \theta}}{\sin \theta} \left(\frac{k}{k_p} \sin \theta + \frac{k}{2k_t} \sin \theta_0 \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

93

An expression relating N to s can be obtained using Eqs. (12) and. (13)

$$\frac{\frac{N}{kl_{t,0}} + \sin \theta_0}{\frac{N}{k_p l_{t,0}} + \sin \theta_0} \left(\cos \theta_0 - \frac{s}{2l_{t,0}} \right) = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{N}{kl_{t,0}} + \sin \theta_0 \right)^2} \quad (14)$$

94

The device can be designed such that the stiffness of the sliding plates (along the direction of their thicknesses) is significantly larger than the stiffness of the toggles (along the direction of their length). In this case, $k_t \ll k_p$, and k can be approximated as

$$k = \frac{k_t}{\frac{k_t}{k_p} + \frac{1}{2}} \approx 2k_t \quad (15)$$

97

with Eqs. (12) and (13) simplifying to

$$N = 2k_t l_{t,0} (\sin \theta - \sin \theta_0) \quad (16)$$

$$s = 2l_{t,0} (\cos \theta_0 - \cot \theta \sin \theta_0) \quad (17)$$

98

and the relationship between N and s is written

$$N = 2k_t l_{t,0} \sin \theta_0 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{(\cos \theta_0 - \frac{s}{2l_{t,0}})^2 + \sin^2 \theta_0}} - 1 \right) \quad (18)$$

99

As illustrated in Fig. 2, the compressive pressure p on the friction plates generated by toggle forces T is assumed to be uniformly distributed between both toggles:

100

$$p = \frac{N}{A_c|_{\max}} \quad (19)$$

101

where $A_c|_{\max} = b_p(l_p - 2d)$ is the maximum contact area of the friction plates under the normal pressure, l_p

102

and b_p are the length and width of the friction plate, respectively, and d is the distance between the toggle

103 and the end of the friction plate. The effective contact area of the friction plates under the normal pressure
 104 depends on the relative displacement between friction plates y with

$$A_c = \begin{cases} b_p(l_p - 2d) & \text{if } 0 \leq y < d \\ b_p(l_p - d - y) & \text{if } d \leq y \leq l_p - d \\ 0 & \text{if } l_p - d < y \leq l_p \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

105 The generated Coulomb friction force F is taken as proportional to the maximum contact area $A_c|_{\max}$

$$F = 2\mu N \frac{A_c}{A_c|_{\max}} \quad (21)$$

106 OR

$$F = \begin{cases} 2\mu N & \text{if } 0 \leq y < d \\ 2\mu N \frac{l_p - y - d}{l_p - 2d} & \text{if } d \leq y \leq l_p - d \\ 0 & \text{if } l_p - d < y \leq l_p \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

107 where μ is the coefficient of friction.

108 3. Dynamic Model

109 In this section, a dynamic model is derived to characterize the behavior of the device under dynamic
 110 sliding motion. The LuGre friction model is selected due to its known simplicity and capability to model the
 111 Stribeck effect and rate dependent friction phenomena [34, 35]. Under the LuGre model, the friction force
 112 F_f is written

$$F_f(x) = \sigma_0 z + \sigma_1 \dot{z} + \sigma_2 \dot{x} \quad (23)$$

113 with

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= \dot{x} - \sigma_0 \frac{|\dot{x}|}{g(\dot{x})} z \\ g(\dot{x}) &= F_c + (F_s - F_c) e^{-(\dot{x}/\dot{x}_s)^2} \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

114 where σ_0 , σ_1 , and σ_2 are constants representing the stiffness of the bristles, microdamping, and viscous
 115 friction, respectively, x is the sliding displacement of the inner friction plate and taken as $x = y_0 - y$ with
 116 $x = 0$ corresponding to the initial location of the sliding plates y_0 as illustrated in Fig.2(b), \dot{x} the sliding
 117 velocity, \dot{x}_s a constant modeling the Stribeck velocity, z an evolutionary variable, $g(\dot{x})$ a function that
 118 describes the Stribeck effect, F_c the Coulomb friction force and F_s the magnitude of the Stribeck effect.

119 Fig. 3 are plots of a typical dynamic response of the VFCC over a harmonic excitation (taken at 0.05 Hz,
 120 ± 13 mm (0.50 in), in the locked position ($s = 20$ mm (0.80 in) or $\theta = 90^\circ$), with $y = 64 \pm 13$ mm (2.5 ± 0.5
 121 in) corresponding to $x = 0 \pm 13$ mm (0.5 in). The asymmetric shape of force-displacement loop is caused
 122 from the effective friction contact area A_c under a constant normal pressure in the friction plate, and could
 123 be modified through altering the geometry of the friction plates. With this configuration, $d < y < l_p - d$
 124 and the Coulomb friction force F_c can be written

$$F_c = \frac{l_p - d - y_0 + x}{l_p - d - y_0} F_{c,0} \quad (25)$$

125 with $F_{c,0}$ representing the initial Coulomb friction force at $x = 0$

$$F_{c,0} = 2\mu N \frac{l_p - d - y_0}{l_p - 2d} \quad (26)$$

Figure 3: Dynamic response of the VFCC at 0.05 Hz, ± 13 mm (± 0.50 in), $s = 20$ mm (0.80 in) ($\theta = 90^\circ$): (a) force-displacement (0.05 Hz) and (b) force-velocity (0.05 Hz).

126 The magnitude of the Stribeck effect F_s is modeled as proportional function of the Coulomb friction force
 127 F_c

$$\begin{aligned} F_s &= \rho F_c \\ F_{s,0} &= \rho F_{c,0} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

128 where $\rho > 1$ is a constant and $F_{s,0}$ is the magnitude of the Stribeck effect at $x = 0$. In this representation,
 129 the initial Coulomb friction force varies with the actuator stroke s . An expression is obtained by substituting

130 N from Eq. (18)

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{c,0} &= 4\mu k_t \frac{l_p - d - y_0}{l_p - 2d} l_{t,0} \sin \theta_0 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{(\cos \theta_0 - \frac{s}{2l_{t,0}})^2 + \sin^2 \theta_0}} - 1 \right) \\
 &= C_c \varphi(s)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{28}$$

131 with

$$\varphi(s) = l_{t,0} \sin \theta_0 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{(\cos \theta_0 - \frac{s}{2l_{t,0}})^2 + \sin^2 \theta_0}} - 1 \right)
 \tag{29}$$

132 In addition, previous investigations [22, 23] demonstrated that constant σ_0 varies linearly with N . Here,
 133 for simplicity, we assume that σ_0 varies linearly with s with

$$\sigma_0 = C_{\sigma_0} s + \sigma_0|_{s=0}
 \tag{30}$$

134 Lastly, also based on previous investigations, all other parameters are taken as independent on s , and
 135 none of the parameters depend on frequency.

136 4. Identification of Model Parameters

137 The parameters of the dynamic models were identified on a prototype subjected to harmonic loadings.
 138 In what follows, the prototype is described, the testing methodology discussed, and results presented. The
 139 subsequent section will validate the identified model on non-stationary excitations. **It should be noted that**
 140 **for the prototype model no consideration was made for parts fabrication from materials suitable for actual**
 141 **use in the unprotected outdoor environment. For actual full scale use, corrosion resistant materials, metal**
 142 **plating, and powder coating technology would be expected to be used on the parts and connections of the**
 143 **device to allow long term use without maintenance.**

144 4.1. Prototype

145 A prototype of the VFCC was fabricated using 3D printing of an acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS)
 146 polymer. **The friction interfaces consist of a metal-free brake and clutch lining (also termed nonmetallic**
 147 **molded strip) pad acquired from McMaster-Carr [36] on a steel plate. The steel plate is used to minimize wear**
 148 **at the friction interface. The nonmetallic pad is used due to its high temperature resistance, high friction,**
 149 **and generally excellent wear resistance [37]. The pad supplier's specification sheet lists a maximum coefficient**
 150 **of friction of 0.47 and an operating temperature up to 480°C. While its wear rate is not provided, the wear**
 151 **rate of a nonmetallic pad made of phenolic resin and glass fiber was reported to be $2.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^3(\text{N}\cdot\text{m})^{-1}$**

152 under sliding speeds below 7 m/s [38]. Note that the VFCC application in civil structure is considered to be
 153 of high intensity over infrequent short periods of time due to the nature of mitigated excitation, whereas it
 154 is hypothesized that the choice of friction material would be adequate. For example, the authors previously
 155 simulated a cast-iron on cast-iron variable friction device used to mitigate wind excitation in [39], and results
 156 show that with the device used in a passive-on regime (full friction), the temperature would only increase by
 157 a maximum of 75°C over 50 seconds, and by a maximum of 60°C over 50 seconds when used in a semi-active
 158 regime. A possible alternative to the metal-free brake and clutch lining pad is a high-strength brake and
 159 clutch lining (also termed semimetallic woven strip) pad, which is rated with a maximum friction coefficient
 160 of 0.51 and an operating temperature up to 500°C [36]. Also, cast-iron on cast-iron could be considered in
 161 the event that clutch lining would pose long-term durability issues. The variation of the friction coefficient
 162 as a function of temperature is not available in the specification sheet from the supplier. However, any
 163 variation in friction would be handled by the controller – the use of the device in a semi-active regime is left
 164 to future work. Because the friction material selected is comparable to that used in automotive/industrial
 165 braking systems, the variation in friction coefficient with operating temperatures is expected to be minimal.

166 A picture of the prototype mounted in an aluminum frame (for testing) is shown in Fig. 4(a) with its
 167 3D printed components shown in Fig. 4(b), and its dimensions listed in Table 1. During test, the actuator
 168 stroke was emulated by using fixed spacers between both toggles.

Figure 4: Picture of the VFCC: (a) prototype mounted in an aluminum frame for testing; and (b) 3D printed components of the prototype.

Table 1: Design parameters of the VFCC prototype.

parameter	variable	value	units
plate length	l_p	165 (6.50)	mm (in)
plate width	b_p	60 (2.36)	mm (in)
initial plates thickness	$h_{p,0}$	50 (1.97)	mm (in)
initial toggle length	$l_{t,0}$	40 (1.57)	mm (in)
toggle width	b_t	20 (0.79)	mm (in)
toggle thickness	h_t	10 (0.39)	mm (in)
toggle to plate end distance	d	45 (1.75)	mm (in)
outer plates distance	H	177 (6.98)	mm (in)
initial angle	θ_0	1.32 (75.6)	rad ($^\circ$)
initial relative plate displacement	y_0	64 (2.50)	mm (in)

169 4.2. Methodology

170 The prototype was mounted in an aluminum frame to restrain the outer sliding friction plates, and the
171 frame installed in a 500 kN (110 k) Servo Hydraulic Material Testing Machine 810. Force and displacement
172 data were obtained from a data acquisition system at 100 Hz. The device was subjected to a displacement-
173 controlled harmonic load during two hours to first wear the lining surfaces in both the forward and backward
174 directions in order to provide a constant surface throughout the sliding areas.

175 After this preparation, the VFCC was subjected to five cycles of displacement-controlled harmonic load of
176 13 mm (0.50 in) amplitude at 0.05 and 0.2 Hz. These tests were repeated under actuator stroke lengths s from
177 0 to 20 mm (0.80 in) in 2 mm (0.08 in) increments. A stroke $s = 0$ ($\theta = \theta_0$) in the tested configuration was
178 set such that friction plates were barely in contact, while $s = 20$ mm (0.80 in) provides a fully locked position
179 ($\theta = 90^\circ$). The initial position $x = 0$ mm provides an average effective contact area $A_{c,0} = b_p(l_p - d - y_0)$
180 under normal pressure, and $x_{\max} = 13$ mm (0.50 in) corresponds to the maximum effective contact area
181 $A_{c,\max} = b_p(l_p - d - y_0 + x_{\max})$.

182 4.3. Results

183 First, constants C_c and ρ are determined from experimental test data. Fig. 5(a) is a plot of the
184 experimental values obtained for $C_c = F_{c,0}/\varphi$ as a function of s , while Fig. 5(b) is a plot of the experimental
185 values obtained for $\rho = F_{s,0}/F_{c,0}$. In both cases, the experimental value can be modeled by a constant (linear
186 fit), except for lower values of the actuator stroke ($s \leq 4$ mm), which could be attributed to an irregular
187 behavior occurring when the normal force N applied onto the sliding plates is low.

Figure 5: Identification of model constants (a) C_c ; and (b) ρ .

188 Second, values obtained for C_c and ρ are integrated in the dynamic model, and parameters σ_0 , σ_1 , and
 189 σ_2 identified by minimizing the error function J :

$$J_i = \| \hat{F}_{f,i} - F_{f,i} \|_2 \quad (31)$$

190 where F_f is the friction force measured experimentally, \hat{F}_f the friction force estimated by the model, i is a
 191 test associated with a given actuator stroke length s , and $\| \cdot \|_2$ is the Euclidean norm. The dependence of
 192 σ_0 on s is estimated using the command `lsqcurvefit` in MATLAB. Fig. 6 is a plot of the estimated values
 193 for σ_0 , along with a linear fit yielding values for C_{σ_0} and $\sigma_0|_{s=0}$. Table 2 summarizes the identified model
 194 parameters.

Figure 6: Plot of σ_0 versus s .

Table 2: Identified model parameters.

parameter	units	value
ρ	–	1.052
C_c	$\text{kN} \cdot \text{mm}^{-1}$ ($\text{kip} \cdot \text{in}^{-1}$)	0.321 (1.834)
C_{σ_0}	$\text{kN} \cdot \text{mm}^{-2}$ ($\text{kip} \cdot \text{in}^{-2}$)	0.043 (6.240)
$\sigma_0 _{s=0}$	$\text{kN} \cdot \text{mm}^{-1}$ ($\text{kip} \cdot \text{in}^{-1}$)	1.302 (7.432)
σ_1	$\text{N} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{mm}^{-1}$ ($\text{lb} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{in}^{-1}$)	0.200 (1.142)
σ_2	$\text{N} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{mm}^{-1}$ ($\text{lb} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{in}^{-1}$)	0.200 (1.142)

195 Figs. 7 and 8 show the experimental data fitting using the model based on the identified parameters
196 listed in Table 2. Plots show the force-displacement and force-velocity loops for two representative stroke
197 lengths: $s = 12$ mm (0.48 in) which represents an unlocked and average actuated stroke length, and $s = 20$
198 mm (0.80 in) which represents the locked position. There is good agreement between experimental data
199 and model values. A higher level of noise occurs under the higher excitation frequency (0.2 Hz) and larger
200 actuator stroke ($s = 20$ mm (0.80 in)). **This noise is likely caused from unsteady contacts between spacers
201 and toggles. The spacers do not attach firmly with the toggles and cause chattering of the normal force on
202 the friction plate under this higher excitation frequency. It is anticipated that this phenomenon would be
203 highly reduced or eliminated when using an actuator that would connect firmly to the toggles.** Fig. 9 are
204 plots of the force-displacement and force-velocity loops obtained from the dynamic model for a harmonic
205 excitation of 13 mm (0.50 in) at 0.05 Hz under various levels of actuator stroke.

Figure 7: Harmonic test at stroke length $s = 12$ mm (0.48 in) (unlocked position): (a) force-displacement (0.05 Hz); (b) force-velocity (0.05 Hz); (c) force-displacement (0.2 Hz); and (d) force-velocity (0.2 Hz).

Figure 8: Harmonic test at stroke length $s = 20$ mm (0.80 in) (locked position): (a) force-displacement (0.05 Hz); (b) force-velocity (0.05 Hz); (c) force-displacement (0.2 Hz); and (d) force-velocity (0.2 Hz).

Figure 9: (a) Force-displacement and (b) force velocity loops for a harmonic excitation of 13 mm (0.50 in) at 0.05 Hz.

206 **5. Model validation under non-stationary excitations**

207 The tuned dynamic friction model is validated using a methodology similar to [22]. The methodology
 208 consists of directly subjecting the device to seismic excitations due to their rich frequency content and varying
 209 amplitudes, representing an extreme input for verification purposes. Note that a direct seismic excitation
 210 input does not necessarily represent the excitation on the device installed into a structural frame, but gives
 211 a useful indication of the device’s dynamic performance under a non-stationary excitation. The seismic
 212 excitations are the 1979 Imperial Valley earthquake and the 1961 Hollister earthquake. The excitation
 213 records were obtained from USGS Station 5155 and USGS Station 1028, respectively, extracted from the
 214 PEER ground motion record database [40]. Ground displacements were computed by double integrating
 215 the ground acceleration data and scaled to a maximum of 10.2 mm (0.4 in) to match the limitations of the
 216 testing equipment at high frequencies. The acceleration and scaled displacement time histories are shown in
 217 Fig. 10.

Figure 10: Earthquake input excitations: (a) unscaled ground acceleration (Imperial Valley earthquake); (b) unscaled ground acceleration (Hollister earthquake); (c) scaled ground displacement (Imperial Valley earthquake); and (d) scaled ground displacement (Hollister earthquake).

218 Figs. 11 to 14 show the experimental data fitting for each seismic excitation under two representative
 219 strokes ($s = 12$ mm (0.48 in) and $s = 20$ mm (0.80 in)). There is good agreement between the experimental
 220 data and the values estimated from the model. The fit of the response to the Imperial Valley earthquake
 221 under $s = 12$ mm (0.48 in) shows a significant underestimation at the end of the time series (Fig. 11(a)),
 222 which can be attributed to a residual force in the testing machine at the end of the test. This phenomenon is
 223 not observed in other results. In addition, there is a small disagreement in the fit at higher stroke (Figs. 13
 224 and 14) when the motion reverses (bottom-right corner of the force-displacement loops). This is attributable
 225 to a small asymmetry in the VFCC that becomes more apparent under higher friction forces, where the
 226 forward and backward forces differ. This asymmetry in forces could be reduced by additional wearing of the
 227 friction plates.

Figure 11: Imperial Valley earthquake at unlocked condition ($s = 12$ mm (0.48 in)): (a) time history of damping force; (b) force-displacement loop; and (c) force-velocity loop.

Figure 12: Hollister earthquake at unlocked condition ($s = 12$ mm (0.48 in)): (a) time history of damping force; (b) force-displacement loop; and (c) force-velocity loop.

Figure 13: Imperial Valley earthquake at locked condition ($s = 20$ mm (0.80 in)): (a) time history of damping force; (b) force-displacement loop; and (c) force-velocity loop.

Figure 14: Hollister earthquake at locked condition ($s = 20$ mm (0.80 in)): (a) time history of damping force; (b) force-displacement loop; and (c) force-velocity loop.

228 6. Conclusion

229 This paper introduced a novel semi-active friction device for connecting a cladding panel to the structural
 230 system. The device, termed the variable friction cladding connection (VFCC), was designed to mitigate
 231 different types of hazards. It consists of two sets of sliding friction plates onto which a variable normal force
 232 can be applied through an actuated toggle system. In a locked position, which is also its passive mode, the
 233 device provides a maximum friction resistance, therefore providing mitigation capabilities versus blast. It
 234 can also be entirely disengaged or actuated in order to mitigate earthquake and wind excitations.

235 A static model was derived to obtain an expression relating the Coulomb friction force to the actuator
 236 stroke. This relationship was then used within a dynamic friction model to characterize the dynamic be-
 237 havior of the device. A prototype VFCC was fabricated using 3D printing and tested to identify the model

238 parameters using harmonic loadings. The tuned dynamic model was validated on non-stationary excitations
239 under various actuator stroke. Results from the harmonic loadings showed that the dynamic model agreed
240 with the experimental data. Results from the non-stationary excitations demonstrated good performance
241 of the model at estimating the response of the VFCC, despite a slight disagreement between the model
242 and experimental data under high actuator stroke that occurred when the sliding direction reversed. This
243 disagreement was attributed to asymmetries in the prototype.

244 The model and experimental results presented in this paper demonstrated that the device could function
245 as designed for providing variable friction capabilities to a cladding connection. Combined with a proper
246 performance-based design methodology and a controller, the VFCC could have great potential at mitigating
247 multi-hazards, either individually or combined. Future work includes testing of the integrated VFCC into
248 a semi-active cladding system resisting blast, wind, and seismic loads, and developing performance-based
249 design methodologies.

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References

- [1] J. Connor, S. Laflamme, Structural motion engineering, Springer, 2014.
- [2] S. Dogruel, G. Dargush, Risk-based multi-hazard optimization of passively damped structures using evolutionary algorithms, in: Proceedings of The 14th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering October 12-17, 2008, Beijing, China, 2008.
- [3] J. Crawford, D. Houghton, J. Karns, Multi-hazard mitigation in steel frame air traffic control towers as a function of redundancy, lateral configuration and connection geometry, in: All-Regional FAA Structural Seminar on Seismic and Progressive Collapse Resistant Structures for Air Traffic Control Towers, 2002.
- [4] J. N. Yang, A. K. Agrawal, Semi-active hybrid control systems for nonlinear buildings against near-field earthquakes, *Engineering Structures* 24 (3) (2002) 271–280.
- [5] S. Laflamme, J. E. Slotine, J. Connor, Self-organizing input space for control of structures, *Smart Materials and Structures* 21 (11) (2012) 115015.

- [6] B. Spencer Jr, S. Nagarajaiah, State of the art of structural control, *Journal of structural engineering* 129 (7) (2003) 845–856.
- [7] F. Ubertini, G. Comanducci, S. Laflamme, A parametric study on reliability-based tuned-mass damper design against bridge flutter, *Journal of Vibration and Control* (2015) 1077546315595304.
- [8] T.-K. Lin, L.-Y. Lu, H. Chang, Fuzzy logic control of a stiffness-adaptable seismic isolation system, *Structural Control and Health Monitoring* 22 (1) (2015) 177–195.
- [9] L. Cao, S. Laflamme, D. Taylor, J. Ricles, Simulations of a variable friction device for multihazard mitigation, *Journal of Structural Engineering* 142 (12) (2016) H4016001. doi:10.1061/(asce)st.1943-541x.0001580.
- [10] G. Ma, Z. Ye, Energy absorption of double-layer foam cladding for blast alleviation, *International Journal of Impact Engineering* 34 (2) (2007) 329–347.
- [11] M. Theobald, G. Nurick, Experimental and numerical analysis of tube-core claddings under blast loads, *International Journal of Impact Engineering* 37 (3) (2010) 333–348.
- [12] C. Wu, L. Huang, D. J. Oehlers, Blast testing of aluminum foam-protected reinforced concrete slabs, *Journal of Performance of Constructed Facilities* 25 (5) (2010) 464–474.
- [13] C. Shim, N. Yun, R. Yu, D. Byun, Mitigation of blast effects on protective structures by aluminum foam panels, *Metals* 2 (2) (2012) 170–177.
- [14] R. Merrett, G. Langdon, M. Theobald, The blast and impact loading of aluminium foam, *Materials & Design* 44 (2013) 311–319.
- [15] B. Goodno, J. Craig, L. El-Gazairly, C. Hsu, Use of advanced cladding systems for passive control of building response in earthquakes, in: *Proceedings, 10th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, July, 1992, pp. 19–24.
- [16] A. Baird, A. Palermo, S. Pampanin, Controlling seismic response using passive energy dissipating cladding connections, in: *2013 NZSEE Conference*, 2013.
- [17] H. Maneetes, A. M. Memari, Introduction of an innovative cladding panel system for multi-story buildings, *Buildings* 4 (3) (2014) 418–436.
- [18] C. Amadio, C. Bedon, Viscoelastic spider connectors for the mitigation of cable-supported façades subjected to air blast loading, *Engineering Structures* 42 (2012) 190–200.

- [19] A. Agrawal, J. Yang, A semi-active electromagnetic friction damper for response control of structures, *Advanced technology in structural engineering* (2000) 1–8.
- [20] S. Narasimhan, S. Nagarajaiah, Smart base isolated buildings with variable friction systems: H controller and saivf device, *Earthquake engineering & structural dynamics* 35 (8) (2006) 921–942.
- [21] Y. Kawamoto, Y. Suda, H. Inoue, T. Kondo, Electro-mechanical suspension system considering energy consumption and vehicle manoeuvre, *Vehicle System Dynamics* 46 (S1) (2008) 1053–1063.
- [22] L. Cao, A. Downey, S. Laflamme, D. Taylor, J. Ricles, Variable friction device for structural control based on duo-servo vehicle brake: Modeling and experimental validation, *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 348 (2015) 41–56.
- [23] A. Downey, L. Cao, S. Laflamme, D. Taylor, J. Ricles, High capacity variable friction damper based on band brake technology, *Engineering Structures* 113 (2016) 287–298.
- [24] C. Ng, Y. Xu, Semi-active control of a building complex with variable friction dampers, *Engineering Structures* 29 (6) (2007) 1209–1225.
- [25] L.-Y. Lu, G.-L. Lin, A theoretical study on piezoelectric smart isolation system for seismic protection of equipment in near-fault areas, *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures* 20 (2) (2009) 217–232.
- [26] G.-L. Lin, C.-C. Lin, L.-Y. Lu, Y.-B. Ho, Experimental verification of seismic vibration control using a semi-active friction tuned mass damper, *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics* 41 (4) (2012) 813–830.
- [27] J. Pardo-Varela, J. Llera, A semi-active piezoelectric friction damper, *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics* 44 (3) (2015) 333–354.
- [28] T. Vesselenyi, S. Dziac, I. Dziac, M.-J. Manolescu, Fuzzy and neural controllers for a pneumatic actuator, *International Journal of Computers Communications & Control* 2 (4) (2007) 375–387.
- [29] A. Mehmood, S. Laghrouche, M. El Bagdouri, Modeling identification and simulation of pneumatic actuator for vgt system, *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical* 165 (2) (2011) 367–378.
- [30] S. S. Sahasrabudhe, S. Nagarajaiah, Semi-active control of sliding isolated bridges using mr dampers: an experimental and numerical study, *Earthquake engineering & structural dynamics* 34 (8) (2005) 965–983.
- [31] M. A. Karkoub, M. Zribi, Active/semi-active suspension control using magnetorheological actuators, *International journal of systems science* 37 (1) (2006) 35–44.

- [32] M. Unsal, C. Niezrecki, C. Crane, Two semi-active approaches for vibration isolation: piezoelectric friction damper and magnetorheological damper, in: *Mechatronics, 2004. ICM'04. Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on*, IEEE, 2004, pp. 60–65.
- [33] M. Amjadian, A. K. Agrawal, A passive electromagnetic eddy current friction damper (pemecfd): Theoretical and analytical modeling, *Structural Control and Health Monitoring*.
- [34] P. Lischinsky, C. Canudas-de Wit, G. Morel, Friction compensation for an industrial hydraulic robot, *IEEE Control Systems* 19 (1) (1999) 25–32.
- [35] K. Khayati, P. Bigras, L.-A. Dessaint, Luge model-based friction compensation and positioning control for a pneumatic actuator using multi-objective output-feedback control via lmi optimization, *Mechatronics* 19 (4) (2009) 535–547.
- [36] McMASTER-CARR. <https://www.mcmaster.com/#friction-material>.
- [37] X. Xiao, Y. Yin, J. Bao, L. Lu, X. Feng, Review on the friction and wear of brake materials, *Advances in Mechanical Engineering* 8 (5) (2016) 1687814016647300.
- [38] B. Öztürk, F. Arslan, S. Öztürk, Effects of different kinds of fibers on mechanical and tribological properties of brake friction materials, *Tribology Transactions* 56 (4) (2013) 536–545.
- [39] S. Laflamme, D. Taylor, M. Abdellaoui Maane, J. J. Connor, Modified friction device for control of large-scale systems, *Structural control and health monitoring* 19 (4) (2012) 548–564.
- [40] Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center (PEER), 2011. PEER Ground Motion Database, available at <http://ngawest2.berkeley.edu/>.